

**STUDENTS' READING COMPREHENSION THROUGH CLOZE
PROCEDURE FOR THE FIRST SEMESTER STUDENTS OF THE ENGLISH
DEPARTMENT AT UNIVERSITAS MUHAMMADIYAH MAKASSAR**

Dr. Ratu Yulianti Natsir, S.Pd., M.Pd.

Uyunnasirah Hambali, S.Pd., M.Pd.

Corresponding author's email: ratu.yulianti@unismuh.ac.id

*^{1,2,3,4} English Education Study Program, Faculty of Teacher Training and
Education, Muhammadiyah University of Makassar, Indonesia*

*Address: Sultan Alauddin Street 259, Makassar City, South Sulawesi Province,
Indonesia, 90221, +62 852-9962-7308*

Abstract: The objective of this study was to investigate the improvement of students' reading comprehension in literal comprehension, which focuses on main ideas and sequence of detail through Cloze Procedure. The researcher utilized a pre-experimental design. The pre-experimental study comprised a pre-test, treatment, and post-test. Thirty students from the first semester of the English Department at Universitas Muhammadiyah Makassar were chosen as the sample for this research using purposive sampling. The reading test obtained the data. The research findings demonstrated that the Cloze Procedure substantially affected the student's reading comprehension. The pre-test has an average score of 3.56, while the post-test has an average score of 7.15. The student's performance in literal comprehension has improved by 76.00%. The t-test findings for the main ideas and sequence of detail are 4.80 and 4.70 greater than the critical value from t-table 2.045. The t-test value exceeds the critical value from the t-table, indicating acceptance of the null hypothesis (H₀). The Cloze Procedure considerably improves students' literal and interpretive reading comprehension, so it is concluded that applying the Cloze Procedure can impact teaching and acquiring reading comprehension more.

Keywords: Reading Comprehension, Cloze Procedure, Improvement

INTRODUCTION

For students, reading is crucial. Reading is a dynamic cognitive activity that entails engaging with written material and evaluating understanding in order to ascertain significance. Readers who are able to derive meaning from written text can acquire new language, comprehend abstract ideas, employ grammatical principles, and acquire knowledge. Students may find it difficult to grasp English, particularly when it comes to interpreting reading material, if they need a fundamental comprehension of the language. Reading comprehension refers to the capacity to understand and grasp the meaning of

words, sentences, and paragraphs, as well as the connections and associations between ideas within a given text. If a student is just able to articulate the words of a text but is unable to grasp its significance, it suggests that the student lacks comprehension of the material. When instructing students for a reading assignment, we can assist them in recognizing and understanding relevant background information. Simultaneously, we ascertain whether the acquired knowledge is adequate for comprehending the text.

Reading comprehension can be approached from both the top-down and bottom-up perspectives. According to Nunan (2004), the bottom-up technique of reading is the process of understanding written symbols, beginning with smaller units (individual letters) and progressing to larger ones (words, clauses, and sentences). Reading comprehension, as described by Olson and Diller (1982), is the set of skills required to comprehend and apply information offered in written texts. In this case, students should be able to learn by reading textual materials. According to Harris and Sipay (1980), reading comprehension ability is a set of generic knowledge acquisition skills that allow people to gain and demonstrate information from written language.

The Cloze Procedure Approach is one strategy for diversifying reading instruction. According to Brown (2000:231), the cloze procedure is a test that teachers use to help students understand reading. Meanwhile according to Heaton (1988:16), the cloze procedure evaluates readers' ability to comprehend text by selecting the most relevant alternatives depending on contextual information offered. Students must be able to read well in order to comprehend English content successfully.

The cloze procedure outperforms the standard reading requirements of matching, reconstruction, and sampling, which makes it useful for teaching reading (Rye, 1982). The reader must not only read the material but also come up with a word that fits a particular situation. The cloze method requires analyzing a distribution of objects to find the missing component. Given the time constraints, the missing word search can be logical or exhaustive (Weaver, 1965).

The teacher whom the researchers interviewed claimed that they found the students' reading comprehension to be severely lacking. By using the Cloze Procedure, the researchers want to increase students' interest in English classes, especially in reading. It was simpler for the students to understand the text's meaning.

Based on the background mentioned above the writer conducted the research under the title "The Enhancement of Students' Reading comprehension through Cloze Procedure for the first semester students of the English Department at Universitas Muhammadiyah Makassar".

METHOD

Pre-experimental design was employed, along with pre-test and post-test designs. Purposive sampling was used to choose thirty students from the first semester of the first semester of the Universitas Muhammadiyah Makassar English Department for this study. The technique for data collection included the following steps: before beginning treatment, students were given a pretest as a fill-in-the-blank and an essay test to assess their comprehension to know the prior knowledge of the students before giving the treatment. After the treatment, the students were given a post-test as a fill-in-the-blank and an essay test to assess their comprehension after the treatment. The researcher provided a score to students' answers based on the indicators listed below: Literal Reading Comprehension dealing main ideas and sequences details:

Indicators	Score
Student locates and uses all relevant information stated directly in the text to answer questions, complete tasks, or otherwise demonstrate clear understanding.	4
Student locates and uses most relevant information stated directly in the text to answer questions, complete tasks, or otherwise demonstrate clear understanding	3
Student locates and uses some relevant information stated directly in the text to answer questions, complete tasks, or otherwise demonstrate clear understanding.	2
Student locates and uses little or no relevant information stated directly in the text to answer questions, complete tasks, or otherwise demonstrate clear understanding	1

(staff.highschool.spsd.org/.../Reading-rubric.)

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

After conducting the research, the researcher received the outcome. The Cloze Procedure used to assess students' reading comprehension reveals variations between their pretest and posttest scores in reading literal comprehension. The data analysis reveals that students' mean scores improve from pretest to posttest. The students' mean pretest score was 3.56, which is classified as poor. However, after the treatment, the students' literal comprehension improved. The students' mean score in the posttest was 7.15, categorized as good. As a result, students' literal comprehension scores improved by 76.00%. The Cloze Procedure effectively improved the students' literal comprehension while reading.

Based on the results of the data analysis, the researcher compared t-test values and t-tables to determine whether the use of the Cloze procedure in teaching reading comprehension was significant. After calculating the t-test value of literal in the main concept, it received scores of 4.80 and 4.70 in a sequence of details; thus, the value of the t-test and t-table in the main idea ($4.80 > 2.045$) and sequence of details ($4.70 > 2.045$). It was determined that the null hypothesis (H_0) was accepted.

The Cloze Procedure allows students to enhance their levels of reading comprehension. Both are literal and interpretive. According to Richards (1995), distinct types of reading comprehension are distinguished based on the text. In this case, the students wanted to create a Cloze Procedure during and after reading. Students could also increase their knowledge of textual components such as orientation, text resolution, character appearance, and moral worth.

According to the findings, the Cloze helped students enhance their reading comprehension and understand what they were reading. Furthermore, the teacher helped students with interpretative questions and literal text.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings, it could be concluded that the technique Cloze Procedure effectively increased students' reading comprehension in terms of the main idea and sequence of details. Seen from the rate percentage of students' scores on the pre-test where students were categorized as poor. After applying treatment using the Cloze Procedure in learning, reading comprehension increased, and more students were categorized as good in the post-test. It is suggested that in teaching literal and interpretative levels of reading comprehension be continually implemented to the students using Cloze Procedure technique.

REFERENCE

1. Brown, H. Douglas, 2000, Principles of Language Learning and Teaching, New Jersey, Prentice Hall Inc.
2. Harris. A. J & E. R. Sipay. (1980). *How to Increase Reading Ability. A guide to Developmental and Remedial Methods, Seventh Edition Revised and Enlarged*. New York: Longman Publisher Inc.
3. Heaton, J.B. (1988). *Writing English Language Tests*. New York: Longman Handbook for Language Teacher.
4. Nunan, D. (2004) *Task-based Language Teaching*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

5. Olson, J.P and M.H Diller. 1982. Learning to Teach Reading in Elementary School. London. MacMillan Publishing Company.
6. Richards, Jacket. 1995. *Longman Dictionary of Applied Linguistics*, Longman House: England
7. Rye, James. 1982. *Cloze Procedure and the Teaching of Reading*. London: Heinemann.
8. Weaver, Wendell W. 1965. *Theoretical aspect of the cloze procedure*. In E.L. Thurston and L.E. Hafner (eds). *The Philosophical and Sociological Bases of Reading*, 19th Yearbook of the National Reading Conference. Newark, Delaware: International Reading Association. (Online), doi : 11 (2) (<http://jlr.sagepub.com/content/11/12/129>)